

Mining Regional Sentiments on Climate Change: A Reddit-Based Analysis of Global North vs
Global South Perspectives

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Abstract

Despite being a globally shared issue, public attitudes and experiences of climate change differ greatly amongst geographical areas. This study explores if location tags included in unstructured Reddit comments may be used to assess the debate on climate change globally by creating a hybrid methodology that maps user comments to geographic locations using data from the r/climatechange subreddit. This methodology combines natural language processing techniques (NLP), user flair analysis, and pattern-based location extraction.

To identify regional differences in climate opinion, the study divides these places into Global North and Global South groups. Users from the Global South commonly express frustration, vulnerability, and concerns rooted in climate injustice, whereas users from the Global North typically participate in solution-oriented or policy-driven discussions with comparatively positive sentiment, according to sentiment analysis using TextBlob.

The study presented in this paper highlights both the promise and drawbacks of employing social media signals for regional climate discourse analysis. The results add to more general discussions about climate communication, digital inequality, and the importance of non-traditional data sources in environmental studies.

Keywords: reddit, climate change, sentiment analysis, geospatial NLP, aggressiveness, climate communication

Introduction

Lately, “social media have become an important platform for public discussions about environmental issues, encompassing topics such as climate change and sustainability” (Kalia, 2013). It is commonplace to consider and base one’s opinion based on information consumed on social media platforms. With an increase in social media platforms, there is an overwhelming amount of information reaching people everyday and it is of great interest to marketing companies, data scientists, content creators, linguists and researchers to understand the type of information that is drawing people’s attention and sparking discussions on social media.

For many years, the media has covered a variety of topics related to global environmental change (Hase V et al., 2021). Climate change discourse varies across geopolitical regions. While the Global North often focuses on policy innovations and technological solutions, the Global South highlights vulnerability, inequality, and climate justice (Uddin, 2017). Social media data mining enables real-time, region-specific analysis of these narratives.

In this study, Python Reddit API Wrapper (PRAW) was used to extract the top 1000 posts and their corresponding comments from the r/climatechange subreddit. The data collected includes post titles, post content, text from comments, and author flair metadata to analyse two key research questions:

How do user sentiments from Global North and Global South differ in climate change discussions on Reddit forum? This study seeks to address this question with the help of a computational framework developed to specifically focusing on three key objectives: mining user reported location signals from comments and metadata, broadly classifying the users into

Global North and Global South categories and analysing aggressiveness and sentiment polarity across countries to understand the difference in climate change discourse patterns.

Can location signals from unstructured Reddit comments be effectively used to study climate change discourse at a global scale? The study offers a systematic framework for mining regional sentiment from Reddit by leveraging user-generated location cues. It aims to uncover how climate change discourse differs between the Global North and Global South, both in emotional tone and thematic focus, based on the lived realities and contextual challenges of these regions. This study aims to specifically understand how techniques for extracting geographic indicators from social media data enable a deeper understanding of regional variations in public sentiment, concerns, and priorities related to climate change.

Method

To analyse regional sentiments on climate change discourse on Reddit data, this study adopts the Computational Social Science approach and the methodology involves four main stages:

Data Collection

For the study, 1000 top-ranked user generated posts and comments were mined from the subreddit r/climatechange using Python Reddit API Wrapper (PRAW). The data collected includes a total of 38,482 post titles, post content, all first-level comments from each post but excluding 'More Comments' structure for better efficiency, and author flair metadata containing location tags. Large sample of posts and comments were used which were subjected to pre-processing steps.

Scrapping Reddit. To collect a representative sample of posts, the PRAW library was used and obtained a Read-Only Reddit instance by collecting the Client ID, Client Secret and User Agent information. PRAW is a Python Reddit API wrapper (PRAW 7.7.0 Documentation).

Location Extraction

To extract user location, a hybrid strategy was adopted. Two primary sources were used within the data to extract user location signals.

User Flair. Author flairs are short customizable tags which appear next to usernames. Many Reddit users display location information voluntarily through flairs (“How Do I Get User Flair?,” 2024). If the flairs are available, they provide a highly reliable indicator of user location (“How Do I Get User Flair?,” 2024).

Comments containing self-reported locations. In the absence of user location flair, a pattern-matching technique was employed to identify self-reported locations. Regular Expressions (regex) were used to search through common phrases for any disclosure of user location. When such a pattern was detected, the location entity was extracted from the comment text.

When both flair and self-reported location was available for the same user, user flair was prioritised as the final location because flairs are explicitly chosen by the user and are less susceptible to contextual ambiguity present in the comments; which would otherwise require lexical, syntactic and semantic-level analysis of text (Hazarika et al., 2018).

Standardizing Locations

Based on the UN and World Bank's socio-economic categorizations, the extracted locations were classified into binary categories - Global North or Global South (World Economic Situation and Prospects et al., 2014)(Kenny & Miles, 2025). This classification was based on widely accepted geopolitical and economic distinctions. This binary classification allowed for a structured regional comparison of sentiment trends across varying socio-economic contexts. The unclassified or ambiguous locations were labeled 'Unknown' and were later omitted from the regional analysis.

Global North. This category includes industrialized, high-income countries like, USA, Canada, UK, Germany, Australia.

Global South. This represents developing or less-industrialized nations, often characterized by lower income levels and higher climate vulnerability (e.g., India, Brazil, Kenya, Indonesia).

Country/Region Classification

To facilitate a country/region-wise sentiment analysis, it was essential to map extracted locations to their corresponding countries to provide a scalable mechanism to evaluate regional emotional responses to climate-related discussions on Reddit. This classification helped analyze and compare climate change discourse between regions with historically differing contributions to climate change and differing experiences of climate change.

Sentiment Analysis

TextBlob, a widely-used Natural Language Processing (NLP) library was used to quantify user attitudes towards climate change (TextBlob: Simplified Text Processing — TextBlob 0.19.0 Documentation, n.d.).

Each comment was assigned a sentiment polarity score ranging from -1 to +1, where -1 represents a ‘Strong Negative’ score, 0 represents ‘Neutral’ score and +1 represents ‘Strong Positive’ score. The scores aimed to capture the emotional tone expressed in each comment which was useful in computing the average sentiment scores for the Global North and the Global South and to compare the distribution of positive, negative and neutral sentiments across regions.

Data Visualization

To compare the mean sentiments of Global North and Global South, bar charts were created.

Separate word clouds were generated for Global North and Global South regions which provided qualitative insights into recurring themes and priorities expressed in each region.

Heatmap was generated to visualize the regional density of comments across different countries, highlighting the volume of climate change discussions originating from specific locations within the Global North and Global South. Seaborn's heatmap functionality was used to display comment density across regions, with a blue color gradient representing comment frequency.

To ensure accuracy, comments where location extraction was unsuccessful or locations labeled ‘Other’ were removed.

Reddit as a Case Study. Reddit's r/climatechange subreddit provides a rich, community-driven dataset for analyzing climate discourse. Unlike platforms dominated by influencers or algorithms, Reddit's threaded discussions and user flair systems enable granular exploration of user demographics, regional affiliations, and argumentation patterns. This study leverages Python Reddit API Wrapper (PRAW) to extract the top 1,000 posts and associated comments from r/climatechange, capturing post titles, content, comment text, and author flair metadata.

Results

Through the study, it was observed that there was a distinct variation in the tone and sentiment of climate change discussions between the Global North and the Global South. The Mean Sentiment Score of the Global North (0.058) and Global South (0.052) are depicted in the bar plot (Fig.1).

Fig 1. Bar Plot depicting Mean Sentiment Score of Global North and Global South regions.

Global North

The comments related to the Global North were mostly neutral to positive (Fig. 2). Technological advancements, legislative fixes, carbon offsets, and personal sustainability initiatives were frequently the topics of discussion. In other areas, there was evidence of climate skepticism, but this was counterbalanced by conversations about mitigation measures.

Fig. 3: Sentiment distribution by Region

Fig. 4: Scatter plot of Sentiment, Region and Location Density

Fig. 5: Plot depicting location density across regions

Fig. 6: Plot depicting Location Density across India, USA, UK, Canada, Australia, EU and other regions

Implications of Findings

The significance of region-specific communication strategies in climate debate is underscored by these findings and suggests Climate organizations and policymakers to:

- Take into account the particular issues and emotional state of users in the Global South.
- Recognize climate justice narratives and go beyond technical fixes.
- Provide inclusive forums so that the voices of underrepresented areas can be heard.

Discussion

Climate change debates are increasingly migrating to online platforms, with social media serving as an informal yet critical record of public sentiment. Platforms like Reddit, X (formerly Twitter), and Facebook have become arenas for global discussions, offering real-time insights into diverse perspectives on environmental crises. While traditional media has long shaped climate narratives, social media now amplifies grassroots voices, democratizes discourse, and reflects the priorities of geographically dispersed communities (Falkenberg et al., 2022).

Social media platforms have emerged as critical spaces for climate change communication, offering real-time insights into public sentiment. Studies highlight their dual role as information hubs and amplifiers of polarization. For instance, Growing polarization around climate change on social media (Nature, 2023) demonstrates how algorithmic curation on platforms like Twitter exacerbates ideological divides, while Social Media's Untapped Potential in the Climate-Change Fight (MIT Sloan, 2022) emphasizes their capacity to mobilize grassroots activism. However, analyses often focus on Western platforms, overlooking linguistic and cultural nuances in Global South contexts.

While it's inspiring to see such passionate engagement, it's important to recognize the nuances involved. The Global North and South present very different narratives and priorities when it comes to climate action. For example, social media users from countries identified as Global North often focus on innovative policies like carbon pricing and renewable energy technologies (Uddin, M. K., 2017). Meanwhile, communities in the South are more likely to highlight issues of climate justice and the urgent need for adaptation strategies, as they face

unique vulnerabilities (Roxburgh et al., 2018). This divergence can sometimes get lost in the homogenized narratives that mainstream media tend to promote, which limits our understanding of the full scope of the climate crisis.

It's like being at a family dinner where everyone is talking over each other - each person's perspective is valid, but without the space to listen and understand, the conversation can quickly become chaotic and unproductive. For years, there's been a blame game between the North and South regarding environmental responsibility, with both sides feeling the pressure to point fingers instead of fostering collaboration. We need to shift this narrative to focus on shared solutions rather than division (Uddin, M. K., 2017).

However, it's crucial to acknowledge the limitations of our study. Our reliance on Reddit, for instance, introduces some sampling bias due to its uneven user distribution. Not to mention, the way we extract location data often relies on users' self-reported information or flair, which isn't always accurate. Plus, using tools like TextBlob for sentiment analysis can miss the mark when it comes to understanding humor, sarcasm, and the complexities of human emotion. It's a reminder that while technology can help us analyze data, it doesn't always capture the depth of human experience.

Looking ahead, there's a world of opportunity for future research. By incorporating data from various languages and regional forums, we can gain a richer understanding of global perspectives. Advanced sentiment analysis tools like BERT could enhance the accuracy of our findings, allowing us to delve deeper into the nuances of online discussions. Additionally,

tracking trends over time could reveal how attitudes evolve in different regions, giving us a clearer picture of the shifting landscape of climate discourse.

Ultimately, the goal should be to create more inclusive dialogues that truly reflect the diverse voices around the world. By fostering understanding and collaboration, we can move towards solutions that benefit everyone, regardless of where they are situated. Let's keep the conversation going - because every voice matters in this fight for our planet.

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